

Direct Estimation of Gold in Geological Samples by Inductively Coupled Plasma Mass Spectrometry

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The methods for the determination of gold and other noble metals have been reviewed by Van Loon and Barefoot¹. Until recently the most favoured method for gold estimation is fire-assay method, after the selection of a representative sample for analysis, because of its ability to deal with larger amounts of samples (25–50 g). The fire-assay procedures vary to a large extent on the skill of the analyst, the exact composition of the ore sample and that of the fusion flux². Atomic absorption spectrometry (AAS), Inductively coupled plasma atomic emission spectrometry (ICP-AES) and Instrumental neutron activation analysis (INAA) in combination with fire-assay pre-concentration step have been used for several years for the determination of gold in a range of geological samples. In recent times the introduction of inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry (ICP-MS) has opened up new possibilities of direct estimation of gold in geological samples because of the features such as high sensitivity and limited interferences³. The present work aims at providing a rapid and sensitive method for the estimation of gold in ore, rock and other industrial samples by ICP-MS especially using smaller amounts of samples. It also describes an effective sample decomposition procedure using aqua regia, bromine, hydrofluoric acid, perchloric acid and hydrogen peroxide.

Results and Discussion

To overcome the problems associated with the uneven distribution of gold, larger amounts of sample have to be taken for analysis. However, ICP-MS technique requires less than 0.4% total dissolved solids (TDS) in the sample solution⁴. Since HF was used to remove silica, which constitutes about 50% of the sample, 1.0 g of sample (in 250 ml) was used to keep TDS in the sample solution within the tolerable limits. The detection limit achieved for gold in practical sample solutions is 0.05 ng ml⁻¹ (for example in a 0.5% solution of PTM-1). Reasonable intensity of the signal can be obtained for gold even with 1.0 g samples when gold is present at as low as 0.01 µg g⁻¹ in the solid sample. The results are presented in Tables 1 and 2.

The effectiveness of the sample decomposition depends mostly on the aqua regia leach which is widely used to decompose geological samples for gold estimation. The success of this technique depends on the ability of aqua regia to dissolve native Au and associated alloys, and phases with Cu and Ag. This property arises from the reac-

TABLE 1—GOLD CONCENTRATIONS (µg g⁻¹) OBTAINED BY ICP-MS USING DIFFERENT WEIGHTS OF THE SAMPLES IN COMPARISON WITH THE VALUES OBTAINED BY FIRE-ASSAY METHOD

Sample	Wt. of g sample	ICP-MS*		Fire-assay**
		With roasting	Without roasting	
GR-13	0.5	25.87	26.30	25.50
	1.0	26.17	26.16	
	2.0	26.01	26.20	
	5.0	26.25	25.97	
K-11	0.5	2.10	1.99	1.65
	1.0	2.05	1.94	
	2.0	1.97	2.16	
	5.0	1.96	2.09	
O-2	0.5	0.02	0.02	Not detected
	1.0	0.01	0.02	
	2.0	0.02	0.02	
	5.0	0.02	0.01	

*Average of six determinations. ** On 50 g sample in each case.

TABLE 2—CONCENTRATIONS (µg g⁻¹) OF GOLD OBTAINED BY ICP-MS IN VARIOUS GOLD REFERENCE SAMPLES BY THE PROPOSED SAMPLE DECOMPOSITION METHOD COMPARED WITH CERTIFIED VALUES

Reference sample	ICP-MS value*	Certified value ^{a,b}
SARM-7	0.32	0.31 ^c
PTC-1	0.63	0.65
PTM-1	1.84	1.8
UMT-1	0.05	0.0482
GTS-1	0.29	0.346
MA-1b	16.58	17.00
CH-1	0.23	0.24
CH-3	1.25	1.40
MA-1a	21.10	21.40
CCU-1b	5.82	5.89
MA-3	7.22	7.48
ASK-3	0.04	0.06 ^c

*Average of six determinations.

^aW. S. Bowman, 1990, CANMET certified reference materials, (CCRMP 90-1E), 63–65. ^bW. S. Bowman, 1994, CANMET certified reference materials (CCRMP 49-1E), 75–78.

^cK. Govindaraju, 1994, compilation of working values and sample description for 383 geostandards, Special issue, *Geostand. Newslett.*, 1994, 18, 5, 38.

tivity of nitrosyl chloride (NOCl) and/or free chlorine formed in freshly prepared aqua regia solution. Aqua regia is found to effectively decompose sulphides including pyrite, arsenides, selenide and some Mo and W minerals. The effectiveness of aqua regia can be enhanced by adding free bromine⁵. The aqua regia-Br₂ mixture is employed to decompose sulphides and other silicates for the determination of Ag and Au by atomic absorption spectrometry⁶. In the present work, we modified this procedure by adding HF to the reaction mixture to attack silicate phases and to facilitate the liberation of Au grains which might not otherwise be wetted by aqua regia-Br₂ alone. Hydrogen peroxide was also used along with HCl to attack many of the sulphide minerals as suggested by O'Leary and Viets⁷.

It was reported that low gold values were obtained for sulphide ores when the analysis is carried out without preliminary sample roasting⁸. One explanation is that aqua regia does not oxidise sulphides to sulphates, and free sulphur separates out, which collects Au and limits the acid-attack on the metal. Roasting of the samples before acid-treatment oxidises the organic and sulphide material present in the sample and prevents the formation of sulphur during sample decomposition. In the procedure using aqua regia, pre-roasting of the sulphide ores is preferred so as to prevent the formation of free sulphur in the reaction mixture which limits the acid attack on gold. Such a pre-roasting of sulphide ores was not found to be essential in the present dissolution procedure as evident from the results presented in Table 1. The oxidation of sulphur and organic material that occurs during roasting is probably accomplished here through Br₂ and repeated addition of both aqua regia and Br₂. In addition, Br₂ is a strong liquid for complexing gold⁹. Hydrogen peroxide was also added for more effective oxidation of sulphides. The results (Tables 1 and 2) also show that comparable values for gold were obtained for different amounts of the same sample indicating that 1 g sample can safely be used to get reasonably dependable data.

The accuracy of the proposed method for the estimation of gold can be assessed from the data obtained on few international standard samples (Table 2). The results are in good agreement with the recommended values. The average values obtained on replicate analysis are within $\pm 7\%$ RSD with comparable accuracy. The method is reliable, rapid, sensitive and can be used for routine application.

Experimental

A PlasmaQuad PQ1 ICP-mass spectrometer was used. Other details of the instrument and the operating parameters are described elsewhere^{4,10}. Gold(¹⁹⁷Au) is a monoisotopic element. Rhodium (¹⁰³Rh) also a monoisotopic element, was used as internal standard to monitor and correct for fluctuations in the matrix, instrumental drift, nebuliser and sampler cone orifice blockage, aerosol transport effects and to minimise any mass-dependent effects. Both these isotopes are relatively free from any

major interference effects.

All solutions were prepared using double-distilled water. AnalaR grade acids and other reagents were used. Commercially available (Spex) 1000 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ standard solutions were used for Au and Rh. Geological reference samples, GTS-1 (gold tailing sample), CH-3 (gold-bearing sulphide ore), MA-1b (gold ore), MA-1a (gold ore), MA-3 (gold ore), CCU-1b (copper concentrate), PTC-1 (noble metal bearing nickel copper matte), UMT-1 (ultramafic ore tailings) were obtained from Canadian Certified Reference Materials Project, Canada. SARM-7 (platinum ore) was obtained from Council for Mineral Technology, South Africa, and ASK-3 (Sulphide ore) from Analytisk Sporelement Komite, Norway. Fire-assaying analysis of the three samples for gold was done at the chemical laboratory of the Hutti Gold Mines Limited, Chitradurga Unit, Karnataka.

Sample preparation : Apart from the above standard reference materials three sulphide ore samples (GR-13, K-11 and O-2) collected from Chitradurga schist belt, Karnataka, were also analysed in these investigations. Each sample was collected on site and it was crushed to 5 mm maximum particle size. The sample was reduced to about 1 kg by coning and quartering. This was ground in a ball mill to 80–100 mesh to provide approximately 200 g. Finally the sample was ground to –230 mesh approximately in an agate mortar and stored in plastic vials.

Sample dissolution procedure : The sample (–230 mesh) decomposition procedure described by Brooks *et al.*⁶ was modified by adding Br₂ to increase the effectiveness of aqua regia to dissolve gold, perchloric acid to increase the temperature of the reaction mixture and HF to attack the silicate phase of the sample. Aqua regia (25 ml), bromine (2 ml), HF (20 ml) and HClO₄ (1 ml) were added to the sample (1.0 g) along with Rh solution (2.5 ml; 10 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$) and kept overnight for digestion. The contents were then evaporated to near dryness on a hot plate at 200°. Then aqua regia (15 ml) and Br₂ (1 ml) were added and the heating continued. The procedure was repeated twice and the contents reduced to about 10 ml by further heating. If the sample contained any undigested black particles (pyrite and chalcopyrite in samples like CCU-1b and PTC-1), these were dissolved by the dropwise addition of H₂O₂ (5–10 ml). Excess H₂O₂ was then removed by gentle heating¹¹ and the final solution made upto 250 ml with double-distilled water. Appropriate amounts of the acids and reagents were used to dissolve samples having other than 1 g amount and diluted accordingly. Blanks were also run wherever necessary. Each sample was dissolved using three replicates and each solution was analysed twice.

The samples were introduced into the ICP-MS by conventional pneumatic nebulisation using a peristaltic pump with a solution uptake rate of about 0.8 ml/min after optimising the instrumental parameters to get maximum sensitivity¹¹. The blank, standard (100 ng ml⁻¹, Au + Rh in 5% HNO₃) and samples were nebulised in that order with at least 4 min of washing of the nebuliser-spray chamber system with 5% HNO₃ between the samples. This was neces-

NOTE

sary to avoid memory problems observed in the case of Au.

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